

Chemical Hazards and Poisons Report

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Editorial

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**Centre for Radiation, Chemical and Environmental
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Welcome to the first Chemical Hazards and Poisons Report published by Public Health England (PHE). Public Health England is a new national executive agency that brings together public health specialists from more than 70 organisations into a single public health service whose mission is to protect and improve the nation's health and wellbeing and to address health inequalities. This report highlights recent examples of this, with the emphasis on multiagency working demonstrated through the wide range of articles, whose authorship includes government, emergency services, housing trusts and citizen groups, as well as PHE staff.

Emergency situations requiring specialised, skilled response occur regularly – be they chemical accidents, deliberate attacks or extreme weather events. A series of articles describes the ongoing preparation for such situations. The Home Office describes its initial operation response policy for blue-light services responding to hazardous material incidents, which is being launched this month, and the Government Decontamination Service explains its work as a source of decontamination and recovery expertise. The public health impact of major incidents can be assessed by setting up a register of people affected by such incidents, a concept that is introduced in a further article.

Air quality – both indoor and outdoor – is an important public health issue affecting all people, young and old, rich and poor, and urban and rural dwellers. In this edition a number of articles reflect on how poor air quality can affect health, and describe scientific projects and programmes to address this. Outdoor air pollution from traffic emissions disproportionately affects those specific communities living closest to main roads and Sheffield City Council has been supporting community groups, who are best placed to know areas of particular local concern, to conduct their own air quality monitoring.

Outdoor emissions contribute to indoor air pollution, but there are additional sources of pollutants inside the home, which is of particular interest as that is where most people, including vulnerable individuals, spend most of their time. PHE staff report the results of a recent analysis of air quality monitoring in a number of properties in response to complaints of ill health by residents. Measures to tackle indoor sources of carbon monoxide are the subject of an article by Halton Housing Trust. The impact of annoyance on public health is also discussed, following an analysis of annoyance reports in Wales, a study which identified such complaints to be significantly associated with deprivation.

And finally – the changing chemical components of our atmosphere can have other, less obvious effects on our health. PHE staff describe how they identified higher-than-expected levels of ultraviolet radiation in April 2013, which led to sunburn reports, due to a temporary decrease in stratospheric ozone.

The next issue of the report is planned for early 2014; please contact us if you would like to contribute to it. Guidelines for authors and a permission to publish form can be found on the website at www.hpa.org.uk/chemicals/reports. Please do not hesitate to contact us about any papers you may wish to submit on chapreport@phe.gov.uk, or call us on 020 7811 7141.

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Front cover images: Car exhaust (© Simon Carruthers), indoor fire, traffic, gas stove, household cleaning products and Beenham compost fire

Recovery, remediation and environmental decontamination – practical aspects associated with developing a recovery strategy following a chemical incident

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Introduction

Chemicals have an important role in the development of human society. However, accidents or chemical incidents, eg during the extraction, manufacture and transport of chemicals, have led to the contamination of the natural environment, resulting in socioeconomic and ecological damage. Chemical incidents can have a large impact on human health and ecosystems, and need to be controlled and managed appropriately. Owing to the necessity for appropriate recovery of an affected environment to protect societies, a UK Recovery Handbook for Chemical Incidents¹ has recently been published by the Health Protection Agency, which is now part of Public Health England. The handbook can be downloaded from the PHE website, and is a technical guidance document, reflecting scientific, technical and societal information relevant to the recovery and restoration of a contaminated environment^{2,3}.

There are few publications or reports in the literature regarding the constraints and effectiveness of the varied and different remediation techniques available. This paper presents an overview of the Aznalcóllar mine spill, which resulted in an extensive metal and metalloids contamination of an ecosystem in Spain in 1998. This incident required a novel long-term recovery strategy never implemented before in response to a chemical incident.

Overview of the incident

The Boliden Apirsa's Aznalcóllar/Los Frailes Silver-Copper-Lead-Zinc mine is 45 km west of Seville, in the south-western corner of Spain. On 25 April 1998, the walls of the pond containing the ore-processing residues from the Aznalcóllar pyrite mine collapsed. This flooded approximately 4,600 hectares of land along the Agrio and Guadiamar rivers with approximately 4 million m³ of acid mine drainage (ie sludge) and 2 million m³ of toxic mine tailings (mine waste considered uneconomic to work) rich in metals and metalloids. On the following days the spill flowed downstream in the Agrio and Guadiamar rivers and threatened the Doñana Natural and National Parks, a UN world heritage area and the largest reserve of bird species in Europe^{4,5}. The acidic water-sludge (mine drainage) was prevented from contaminating

the Doñana ecosystem by several temporary walls. However, the agricultural soils and sediments along the course of the Agrio-Guadiamar river system were severely impacted by metals and metalloids that are highly toxic to human health and ecosystems, such as arsenic, copper, cadmium, lead, zinc and other sulphide-related elements⁶. A total area of 4,286 hectares was covered by a mud layer averaging 7 cm in thickness⁷. The accident resulted in significant socioeconomic and ecological damage, mainly to the agricultural activities of the Guadiamar valley, and attracted worldwide media attention⁸.

Clean-up and recovery process

The area affected (the Agrio and Guadiamar rivers) are surrounded by marshes and include a natural park and national park of great ecological value in close proximity. A natural park is an area of special diversity, uniqueness and beauty, which is suitable for recreational purposes. A national park is an area of great ecological value, with unique biodiversity and beauty (equivalent to a protected area in the UK) in which public access is restricted and which cannot be put to economic use. As a result, immediate recovery/remediation was required. The first phase of clean-up involved physical removal of the toxic mine tailings and sludge. This was done manually by mechanical excavation, using specialised machinery to protect the soil⁶. However, the levels of contaminants in the soil remained significant and two more similar clean-up phases were required in 1999 and 2000^{9,10}. After each clean-up phase, the soils affected were treated by the use of additives and were enhanced with ploughing methods. The objectives of these remediation measures were to immobilise elements to protect groundwater systems and prevent the spread of contaminants, and also to increase soil pH and improve land fertility¹¹. Soil treatments were applied in the following order¹⁰:

- Phase one** application of organic matter and calcium rich additives (1998)
- Phase two** liming with sugar-refinery scum (1999)
- Phase three** application of organic matter plus iron-rich clay materials (2000)

Long-term recovery options

The high levels of metals and metalloids involved in the Aznalcóllar mine spill and their physicochemical characteristics (persistent in soils and water environments), made a reduction in the total concentration of these substances in the Agrio-Guadiamar ecosystem

impractical. These special circumstances resulted in the implementation of two long-term recovery options that had not been implemented before over such an extensive area (4,600 hectares of land). One encompassed the whole ecosystem restoration through the recovery and restoration of plants and animals, land and fluvial system, and was entitled the *Ecological Green Corridor* (EGC) of Guadiamar. This recovery strategy was in effect assisted natural attenuation, and was based on phyto-management (also called phyto-remediation), involving the application of soil additives (organic matter and calcium-rich material) and re-vegetation of the affected area with native woody plants^{11,12}. The EGC programme started in January 1999 and is still ongoing. During this time (14 years after the initial incident) an advanced stage of ecological regeneration and recovery has been observed. Recovery and re-establishment of the river has been very successful and the vegetation is also significantly improved. The functionality of this EGC programme has also been reflected in the recovery and re-colonisation of fauna⁹.

The second long-term remediation option implemented was the construction of a *Permeable Reactive Barrier* (PRB) in the alluvial aquifer of the Agrio river in September 2000^{6,8}. An alluvial aquifer is an area of water-bearing sand and gravel typically found near lakes and rivers. A PRB consists of a layer of reactive material buried in a narrow trench, which treats the contaminated groundwater as it flows through the reactive material. The PRB built in the Agrio aquifer was based on the only PRB for acid mine drainage described in the literature at that time⁶. The reactive material within the PRB used in this incident included a mixture of calcite (CaCO_3), vegetal compost (a mixture of decaying vegetal matter), iron and sewage sludge, which provides a continuous neutralisation of pH and removal of metals from groundwater within the PRB^{6,8}. The PRB is still functioning and in place and has been up to 95% effective¹³.

Effectiveness of the recovery options implemented

When identifying an appropriate recovery strategy (ie what recovery options should be considered) it is important to assess and appraise the effectiveness and constraints of all available techniques. An overview of the recovery options associated with the remediation and restoration of the environment following the Aznalcóllar mine spill, is given below.

Effectiveness of implemented recovery options

- Rapid construction of walls to protect the Doñana Natural Park was effective, as it prevented the spill from entering the park
- Removal of toxic sludge (acid mine drainage) from the Guadiamar river 'in dry' was successful. This 'in dry' process involves constructing cofferdams (walls) in the river, the evacuation of water and the subsequent removal

of sludge, working in the same direction as the natural flow of the river

- Implementation of the EGC programme has been successful and reliable for the restoration of an ecosystem damaged by high quantities of persistent metals and metalloids
- Application of soil additives, ploughing methods and re-vegetation (phyto-management) was effective in stabilising metals and metalloids in soils, thus limiting the potential for leaching into groundwater systems
- Phyto-management was effective in improving the fertility of affected soil
- The EGC programme has improved the landscape and provided an opportunity for increased recreational activities, which has had positive socioeconomic benefits in the community
- The PRB continues to neutralise the pH and facilitate removal of metals from groundwater in the alluvial aquifer of the Agrio river

Considerations and constraints

- The mechanical cleaning and removal processes carried out involved heavy machinery, which may have buried toxic residual tailings within the soil
- Use of heavy machinery and large vehicles during the clean-up phases (ie physical removal of the toxic mine tailings and sludge) may have resulted in large amounts of aerosolised contaminants
- Soil additives should have low metals and metalloids content, and an appropriate content of nutrients and substances to treat the contaminated soil
- The EGC programme is a very slow process and has required continuous surveillance (sampling and monitoring), which can be expensive and require specialist skills for sampling and analysis
- Plants used for phyto-remediation absorb contaminants from the soil. These plants are known as accumulator plants. They should be resistant to the contaminants involved, grow quickly and not accumulate high concentrations of pollutants into their leaves and fruit because of the risk of entry into the food chain
- The complexity of the internal structure of the Agrio alluvial deposits affected the design of the PRB. Owing to the design requirements, the heterogeneities of the filling material in the PRB resulted in preferential flows within the PRB, which impacted on capture of the contaminated plume in the groundwater
- Compost used to fill the PRB showed poor degradability which prevented the complete reduction of the sulphate pollutants

Conclusions

Reclamation of an ecosystem extensively affected by metals and metalloids is a very slow process, and complete restoration may not be possible. The natural structure of an ecosystem may affect the dispersion of contaminants following a chemical incident, resulting in a heterogeneous distribution of pollutants, and thus impede their removal. The complex natural structure of the Agrío-Guadamar river system and valley influenced the effectiveness of recovery options implemented to remediate the environment following the Aznalcóllar mine spill.

The success of any clean-up process is linked to the distribution of contaminants within the environment, with the success of clean-up seen to decrease linearly with increasing heterogeneity of distribution. Thus, a geochemical and biological study of the area should be carried out prior to the selection of the recovery options.

The cleaning-removal processes applied in response to the Aznalcóllar mine spill have been successful but are not sufficient to recover the agricultural land used. However, the implementation of long-term recovery options, such as an assisted natural remediation (the EGC programme) and the construction of the PRB have been shown to be effective for economic and social restoration purposes. Through the improvement of the landscape the EGC programme has provided a new land use for the area contaminated, that provide economic benefits for the community affected. This programme has also introduced projects to promote conservation and protect biodiversity, enhancing the public awareness of environmental protection.

The UK Recovery Handbook for Chemical Incidents is available at

<https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/public-health-england/series/recovery-remediation-and-environmental-decontamination>

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